

EVALUATION OF THE BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES, PHARMACOGNOSTIC PROPERTIES, AND PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF *TERMINALIA IVORENSIS* A. CHEV. BARK EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT:

For thousands of years, nature has supplied medicinal agents. Today, a remarkable number of pharmaceuticals have been derived from natural sources. The *Terminalia ivorensis* A. Chev. is a member of the Combretaceae family. This plant is used to treat a variety of illnesses by traditional faith healers. Many phytochemicals are present in it, especially the phenolic group, which produces antioxidants. It's significant to screen for phytochemicals and determine their biological value. Assessing the antioxidant, anthelmintic, antibacterial, phytochemical, and pharmacognostic qualities of bark was the aim of this investigation. Tannins, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, steroids, and glycosides were all present in the bark's hydromethanolic extract. The anthelmintic activity was tested on earthworms. As a positive control, albendazole, a common anthelmintic, was employed. The microorganisms *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli* were subjected to antimicrobial screening using Gentamycin as the standard. Phytochemicals such as flavonoids, tannins, and polyphenols may be involved in the extract's antibacterial and anthelmintic properties. With an IC 50 value of 75.51 µg/ml, the extract showed a significant capacity for radical scavenging when the antioxidant activity of HME was evaluated using the DPPH technique. These findings suggest that the bark of the plant could be a helpful natural remedy for a variety of ailments.

Keywords: *Terminalia ivorensis*, anthelmintic, antibacterial, phytochemicals.

INTRODUCTION:

In addition to their numerous other uses, plants are considered to be an important and essential source of medicines for our everyday needs. Every part of the plant has great significance in herbalism. Alkaloids, glycosides, phenolics, flavonoids, phytosterols, saponins, resins, tannins, and even terpenoids are hence important byproducts that are stored in various parts of the plant bodies. Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, wound-healing, anti-Alzheimer, anticancer, and other therapeutic qualities of plants are therefore ascribed to their existence of significant phytoconstituents¹. Moreover, plant components are found in up to 25% of modern medications. About 8,000 plant species—of which 30% are trees, 32% are herbs, 20% are shrubs, 12% are climbers, and 3% are epiphytes, grasses, lichens, ferns, and algae—are used in Indian medicine.² Studies on anthelmintic drugs are scarce, despite the fact that parasitic worm infections constitute a serious issue³. Helminthiasis is commonly managed using the synthetic anthelmintic medications that are already on the market. However, these medications have significant side effects, including hepatotoxicity, nausea, vomiting, dizziness, headaches, diarrhoea, and stomach discomfort. Finding anthelmintic drugs that are more effective and have fewer side effects is therefore crucial⁴. Infectious diseases caused by microbes remain a serious global health concern. These diseases have historically increased morbidity and mortality rates worldwide and posed serious hazards to the health of both humans and animals. In recent years, antibiotic resistance has become a significant global issue. The necessity of developing new antimicrobial drugs is highlighted by this dilemma as well as the issue of microbial persistence. These novel medications must successfully eradicate persistent microbes, shorten treatment durations, and fight drug-resistant bacteria⁵. With approximately 250 species worldwide, Terminalia is the second largest genus in the Combretaceae family, with the majority of its species being medium- to large trees. The Latin word "terminus" is the source of the name "Terminalia," indicating that the leaves are found at the termination of the branch. Many Terminalia species have branches that are organised in a stepwise fashion, and their bark looks to be cracked off the stem⁶. The *Terminalia ivorensis* A. Chev., often called Idigbo, is a member of the Combretaceae family. This tall, huge, straight deciduous forest tree is found in South Asia, Africa, and Central America⁷. When young, the bark is smooth and light grey, but as it ages, it becomes blackish and sometimes breaks off from lengthy fissures. *T. ivorensis* blooms from April to June in its natural habitat, though this can change elsewhere. Shingle wood, brimstone wood, satin wood, black afara black bark, and yellow terminalia are some common names for *T. ivorensis*. For a variety of traditional medical

uses, various parts of this plant have been used by numerous civilisations. In this study, we tried to look into the bark hydromethanolic extract's anthelmintic, antibacterial, phytochemical, and pharmacognostic qualities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Plant collection and authenticity

Using Voucher No. 0771, Dr. K. Madhava Chetty, Assistant Professor in the Botany Department of S.V. University in Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, confirmed *Terminalia ivorensis* A. Chev. I saved that voucher specimen for later use. The plant bark was dried in the shade for several days before being coarsely powdered and extracted.

Analysis of organoleptic

The term "organoleptic" describes something that is detectable by the senses of taste, smell, touch, and appearance. Sense and thereby determine specific characteristics of the substance, which can be considered a first step in identifying its identity and degree of purity⁸⁻⁹. The dried bark and extracts of the *T. ivorensis* plant were gathered, analysed, and enumerated for several attributes, such as yield, size, colour, taste, touch, odour, and consistency.

Examination of foreign substances

A thin layer of the drug sample (100–500 g) or the maximum amount recommended in the monograph should be spread out. The unaided eye or a 10x lens should be used for inspection in order to identify the foreign material. Once it has been separated and weighed, determine what percentage is present¹⁰⁻¹¹.

The evaluation of physicochemical

As far as possible, medicinal plants should be free of mildew, insects, and other animal pollutants. The pharmacopoeia monograph states that the amount of foreign materials in a product should not exceed the standard that is controlled. To undertake the physical evaluation of crude medications, a variety of physico-chemical techniques are employed to ascertain certain physical constants¹¹. The drying loss, extractive values, and ash values were calculated in accordance with the formal protocols described in WHO guidelines on quality control methods for medicinal plant materials¹⁰.

Index of froth and swelling

Gums and medications that include high levels of mucilage, pectin, or hemicelluloses are particularly useful for therapeutic or medical purposes due to their capacity to swell. The foaming index measures how much an aqueous decoction of extracts of medicinal plants

foams. An agitated aqueous infusion may produce a persistent froth due to saponins¹¹⁻¹². The WHO guidelines' methods were used to calculate the swelling and foaming indices¹⁰.

Observation of fluorescence

When various chemicals and solvents are applied to plant material, the chemical components present display a phenomenon called fluorescence. The current work investigated the fluorescence of powdered *T. ivorensis* plant bark under UV and visible light/daylight settings following treatment with different agents and solvents. A little amount of dried and finely powdered material was treated with a variety of solvents, alkaline solutions, and freshly prepared acids. The powder sample was treated with acids such as concentrated HNO₃, 1N HCl and 1N H₂SO₄, and acetic acid in addition to alkaline solutions such as 1N alcoholic & aqueous NaOH and different solvents such as ammonia, distilled water, 5% FeCl₃, iodine, methanol, and ethanol. Their fluorescence in visible and ultraviolet light was studied¹³⁻¹⁴.

Preparation of plant extract & Phytochemical screening

Soxhlation is required when the contaminant is insoluble in a solvent and the desired substance has limited solubility in that solvent. If the prescribed component is highly soluble in a solvent, it can be extracted from the insoluble material using a simple filtration procedure. Instead of passing many quantities of heated solvent through the sample, this method has the advantage of reusing a single batch of solvent. This method cannot be used for thermolabile compounds since prolonged heating can degrade the substance. The bark of *T. ivorensis* was successfully dried and extracted using a Soxhlet system and a sequential solvent extraction process, which used solvents with increasing polarity such as petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, hydromethanolic, and water. The residue was dried and extracted using the subsequent solvent once each extraction was finished. To remove any debris, the extracts were filtered through muslin fabric and concentrated. Afterward, the extracts were allowed to air dry. Colour, consistency, and yield percentage were calculated. The concentrated extracts were put through a qualitative test in accordance with standard protocols to identify different phytochemical ingredients^{11, 15-16}.

Microscopic powder analysis

With the use of an electric grinder, shade-dried barks were ground into a fine powder. Using the standard methods, powder microscopy was performed on this fine powder^{11,17}.

Assessment of anthelmintic action

The efficacy of hydromethanolic extract of bark as anthelmintics against *Pheretima posthuma* was investigated. The paralysis and death periods of the worms were assessed using a bioassay at extract concentrations of 10, 25, and 50 mg/ml. The control was saline water, and the standard reference was albendazole. Adult Indian earthworms were used for the test. Before being employed for anthelmintic research, earthworms were thoroughly cleaned with normal saline after being removed from damp soil. The earthworms were divided into four groups of six each. Small amounts of the extract were mixed with water, and the volume was then adjusted to 20 millilitres using saline water. In petri dishes, extract and standard drug solutions were added. All of the earthworms were placed in a 20 ml solution that contained hydromethanolic extract (ratios of water and methanol 30:70) and albendazole in different concentrations. The duration required for individual worms to become paralysed and die was recorded. It was time for paralysis when there was no movement keep when the worms were agitated violently. When immersed in heated water (50⁰C), the worms lost their ability to move, and their body colours started to fade, indicating their death ¹⁸⁻¹⁹.

Assessment of microbial inhibition

All Petri plates and graduated measurement pipettes were sterilised by heating them to 120 degrees Celsius for one hour in an autoclave. An autoclave was used to steam sterilise the material for 20 minutes at 121 degrees Celsius (15 psi). The nutritional agar used to make each plate was the same thickness. The well plate method was used to conduct the antimicrobial test. Through dissolution in water, three test concentrations of the hydromethanolic extract were created: 200, 400, and 600 µg/ml. The standard gentamycin concentration was 10 µg/ml. The control used was water. A sterile borer was used to scrape off media from a petri dish that had been injected with the organisms, creating bores with a diameter of 5 mm. Petri dishes were then incubated at 37 °C after the solutions of each test substance and reference standards were added individually. The zones of inhibition were assessed following an overnight incubation period ²⁰.

Assessment of antioxidant activity by DPPH method:

1. Making a hydro methanolic solvent (30:70 v/v):

Add thirty millilitres of distilled water to seventy millilitres of methanol. The extract and DPPH solution will be dissolved using this.

2. making a solution of plant extract:

Weigh a reasonable amount of the powdered plant extract (10 mg). Dissolve it in ten millilitres of hydro methanolic solvent to create a stock solution containing 1 mg/mL. For testing, create serial dilutions at 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/mL.

3. Making a solution of DPPH:

To make a 0.1 mM solution, weigh 3.94 mg of DPPH and dissolve it in 100 mL of hydro methanol (30:70 v/v). Keep the solution away from light.

4. The process of making ascorbic acid:

Weigh out 1.76 mg of ascorbic acid and dissolve it in 100 mL of hydro methanol (30:70 v/v) to create a 0.1 mM solution. Ascorbic acid is air and light sensitive. The solution should be kept in an amber-colored bottle.

5. The method of assay:

With a few modifications, the plant extract's ability to scavenge free radicals was assessed using the technique described by Swapnil S. L. et al. using DPPH. To 1 mL of plant extract solution in different strengths, add 2 mL of DPPH solution. For half an hour, incubate at room temperature in the dark. The absorbance at 517 nm should be measured with a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer. ²¹

The blank solution:

For base line correction, use 3 mL of hydro methanol solvent (absorbance: 0.000).

Solution of control:

Combine 2 mL of DPPH solution with 1 mL of hydro methanol solvent. Measure absorbance after incubating as described above.

Sample: 1 mL of plant extract plus 2 mL of DPPH solution

Standard: Ascorbic acid (As with the plant extract, use the same series of dilutions.)

The percentage scavenging activity of the plant extract was calculated using the formula below.

Scavenging activity is expressed as $(A_b \text{ control} - A_b \text{ sample} / A_b \text{ control}) \times 100$.

where the absorbance of the sample is indicated by $A_b \text{ sample}$ and the absorbance of the control by $A_b \text{ control}$.

Calculation of IC₅₀:

Plot the concentration (X-axis) against the percentage inhibition (Y-axis).

OUTCOMES AND DISCUSSION:

Sensory evaluation

It is a crucial metric for the qualitative characterisation of the morphological and sensory features of plant bark and extracts. The characteristics, colour, taste, smell, size, consistency, and touch listed in Tables 1 and 2 were found during the investigation.

Table 1: Organoleptic properties of *T. ivorensis* bark

Attributes	Description
Colour	Grayish-brownish
Smell	Feature
Taste	Astringent
Size	Varies in sizes depend on age
Touch	Rough externally, smooth internally but fibrous

Table 2: Organoleptic results of various extracts of bark

Properties	Pet. Ether	Chloroform	Ethyl acetate	Hydro methanolic	Water
Colour	Yellowish-green	Greenish-back	Greenish-brown	Blackish-brown	Brownish
Odour	Agreeable	Agreeable	Agreeable	Agreeable	Agreeable
Consistency	Sticky	Sticky	Resin like	Semisolid resin	Sticky paste
% Yield	0.8 %	1.12 %	1.21 %	6.32 %	7.53 %

Fig. 1. Pet. ether extract

Fig. 2. Chloroform extract

Fig. 3. Ethyl acetate extract

Fig. 4. Hydromethanolic extract

Fig. 5. Water extract

Examining foreign substances

The presence of undesired and extraneous material that is not a part of the original plant material is indicated by this quality control test. The quality and purity of plant materials are evaluated using this test. Table 3 tabulates the result obtained.

Table 3: Foreign matter analysis

Analysis of foreign matter	Percentage (%) W/W
Total foreign matter	Below 0.001

Physical-chemical analysis

In order to accomplish the various goals of evaluating crude medical products, including determining their identity, purity, and quality, physical evaluation procedures are effectively employed. Data on drying loss, ash values, extractive values in different solvents, swelling index, and foaming index are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Physicochemical Specifications

Attributes	Values % (w/w)
LOD	9
Total amount of ash	5
Water soluble ash	1.4
Acid insoluble ash	2.7
Index of Swelling	Not present
Index of Foaming	Below 100
Values of Extraction % (w/w)	
Petroleum ether	0.049
Chloroform	0.0706
Ethyl acetate	0.106
Hydromethanolic	0.468
Water	0.627

Observation of fluorescence

The powder sample was treated with a variety of compounds to examine its fluorescence behaviour under visible, short, and long light; Table 5 summarises the results of the study.

Table 5: Examination of fluorescence observations

Treatments	Visible	UV short (254nm)	UV long (365nm)
Powder	Brown	greenish brown	Brown
Powder + Distilled water	Light brown	Dull yellow	Dull green
Powder+ 5% FeCl ₃	Brown	Brownish green	Green
Powder + Iodine	Dark blue/black	Blackish brown	No fluorescence
Powder +1N NaOH (aqueous)	Brown	Dull green	Bright green
Powder +1N NaOH (alcoholic)	Brownish yellow	Green	Yellowish green
Powder + CH ₃ COOH	Pale brown	Yellowish brown	Dull green
Powder + Conc. HNO ₃	Reddish brown	Dull red	Orange/reddish
Powder + 1N HCl	Light brown	Dull yellow	Yellow green
Powder + 1N H ₂ SO ₄	Blackish brown	Reddish brown	Bright red
Powder + Ammonia	Light brownish green	Bright green	Fluo green
Powder + Ethanol	Pale brown	Greenish yellow	Bright green
Powder + Methanol	Yellowish brown	Bright green	Fluo yellow-green

The colour that plant materials release when exposed to UV light as a result of reagent reactions or natural compounds can be used to identify them using fluorescence analysis. Flavonoids, phenolics, and tannins are frequently indicated by green, yellow, or red fluorescence. The presence of starch is confirmed when iodine turns black or blue. Polyphenols and other polar chemicals are frequently extracted by methanol and ethanol. Tannin concentration is indicated by a ferric chloride reaction that turns green or black. Strong fluorescence is frequently produced by phenolic groups in alcoholic and aqueous NaOH (Table 5). Every kind of material has a distinct, vivid colour. diverse plant materials yield diverse colours when exposed to various chemicals and solvents ²²⁻²³.

Testing for phytochemicals

The bioactive components varied depending on the extract type and extraction method. Therefore, using the normal procedure outlined in the methodology section, the extracts underwent initial phytochemical screening. Verification of the chemical makeup of the active ingredients in the plant extract is aided by chemical testing. The hydromethanolic extract had the highest concentration of secondary metabolites, according to the results, as indicated in Table 6. It was therefore used further in each of the examinations that followed.

Table 6: Preliminary assessment of various bark extracts' phytochemical composition

Name of compound	Petroleum ether	Chloroform	Ethyl acetate	Hydro methanolic	Water
Tannins & Phenolic cpds	--	--	--	+++++	+++++
Flavonoids	--	+	--	+++	+
Steroids	--	--	--	+++	+
Saponins	--	--	--	--	+
Glycosides	--	--	+++	+++	+
Alkaloids	--	--	+	--	+++
Amino acids	--	--	--	--	--
Proteins	--	--	--	+++++	+++++
Carbohydrates	--	--	+	--	--

(Where – Absent, + Slightly significant, +++ Moderately significant, +++++Highly significant)

Powder microscopic examination

Xylem fibre: They have blunt ends and a long, cylindrical form. may appear alone or in clusters. They give the plant mechanical assistance (Fig.6).

Starch grains: These are small to medium sized, primarily simple, occasionally rounded, oval, or spherical in shape, and they are found alone rather than in compounds (Fig.7).

Brownish matter or tannin content: Terminalia barks frequently have brown masses that indicate phenolic and astringent chemicals (Fig.8).

Cork cells: They were organised as small, polygonal to rectangular units and stacked. Because it contains suberin or tannins, it has a brownish colour and protects the plant stem (Fig.9).

Phloem parenchyma: It manifests as densely packed cells with horizontal striations or radial alignment. Involved in the transportation of organic nutrients, they are typically brown to dark brown in hue. When evaluating crude drugs, all of these characteristics help to maintain the identity and quality (Fig.10).

Fig. 6. Xylem fibre

Fig. 7. Starch grains

Fig. 8. Brownish matter

Fig. 9. Cork cells

Fig. 10. Phloem parenchyma

Anthelmintic efficacy

Higher extract concentrations decreased the time to death for all worms and produced paralysis significantly earlier, according to the current study. The hydromethanolic extract demonstrated the quickest time of paralysis (P) and death (D) at a dosage of 50 mg/ml, suggesting dose-dependent anthelmintic activity. Albendazole was utilised as a reference standard to evaluate the anthelmintic activity (Table 7). These results imply that plant extracts high in these substances, such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and tannins, may be a useful substitute for synthetic anthelmintic medications, providing a safer and more natural means of managing parasitic diseases. Tannins have been found to be responsible for preventing the development and movement of several helminth stages. Direct damage to the worm's cuticle and hypodermis may cause it to become immobile and eventually die. Phenolic substances' potent antioxidant properties can enhance the host's overall health and indirectly aid in the anthelmintic activity. Additionally, they have the ability to disrupt the parasites' metabolic functions. Known for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, flavonoids can disrupt the energy metabolism of helminths, decreasing their viability and making removal easier²⁴⁻²⁷.

Table 7: The hydromethanolic bark extract's *in vitro* anthelmintic properties

Group	Concentration (mg/ml)	Paralysis (min)	Death (min)
Normal	-----	-----	-----
Hydromethanolic extract	10	32	39
	25	23	27
	50	15	21
Albendazole	25	18	25

Fig. 11. Graphical representation of anthelmintic activity

Fig. 12. 10 mg/ml extract

Fig. 13. 25 mg/ml extract

Fig. 14. 50 mg/ml extract

Fig. 15. 25 mg/ml (Albendazole)

Antimicrobial activity

Table 8: Inhibition zone

Organism	Plant extract ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			Standard ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
	200	400	600	
S. aureus	--	6	9	10
Inhibition zone (mm)	--	6	9	13
E.coli inhibition zone (mm)	--	5	8	10

The antibacterial activity assessed on the bacterial strains *S. aureus* and *E. coli* using the agar well diffusion method. Table 8 displays the inhibition zone of the sample and standard against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. The minimal inhibitory concentration, or MIC, was determined to be 400 $\mu\text{l/ml}$. At 600 $\mu\text{l/ml}$, the extract demonstrated significant efficacy against *S. aureus* in comparison to *E. coli*. According to the findings, this extract may be utilised to treat bacterial illnesses brought on by *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Because the extract contains flavonoids, phenolic substances, and tannins, it has antibacterial properties. Phenolic chemicals are what cause microbial DNA, protein, and lipids to be damaged; tannins work by disrupting

cell walls and precipitating proteins. Flavonoids that disrupt cell membranes and prevent the production of nucleic acids²⁸⁻³⁰.

Fig. 16. *S. aureus*

Fig. 17. *E. coli*

Antioxidant activity by DPPH method:

Chemicals that have a single unpaired electron are called free radicals. Health problems are associated with these free radicals. Antioxidants, which are vital for protecting the body from oxidative stress, which is connected to several chronic diseases, are among the many health benefits of medicinal plants. The radical is neutralised when an antioxidant reacts with an unpaired electron. The free radical DPPH has a rich violet hue in solution and is stable at room temperature.³¹ By contributing an electron or hydrogen, an antioxidant, like a plant extract, can reduce DPPH and cause a solution to become pale yellow. The degree of fading indicates the strength of the antioxidant. DPPH provides a rapid and easy way to evaluate antioxidants. These chemicals, which include flavonoids, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, and alkaloids, function to neutralise free radicals and protect cells from oxidative stress by scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS), preventing lipid peroxidation, and metal ion chelation. For example, flavonoids neutralise free radicals by giving them hydrogen atoms. polyphenols form stable antioxidant complexes, which stop more oxidative damage. The antioxidant defence systems of cells are strengthened by terpenoids, and alkaloids may shield mitochondria from oxidative damage. The combined effects of these bioactive substances in herbal extracts increase their potential as a treatment for illnesses linked to oxidative stress.³² The results of the plant extract and ascorbic acid's ability to scavenge free radicals against the DPPH radical are shown in Table 9, and the data is graphically represented in Figure 18.

Table 9: % inhibition of hydro methanolic extract of *T. ivorensis* bark and standard ascorbic acid against DPPH at 517nm

Concentration $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Absorbance of extract	% inhibition of extract	Absorbance of Ascorbic acid	% inhibition of Ascorbic acid
10	0.815	11.89%	0.705	23.783%
20	0.725	21.621%	0.600	35.135%
40	0.620	32.97%	0.475	48.648%
60	0.540	41.62%	0.355	61.621%
80	0.440	52.42%	0.255	72.432%
100	0.343	62.91%	0.165	82.162%

According to Table 9, ascorbic acid demonstrated a percentage inhibition of 82.162% at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, whereas hydro methanolic extract demonstrated a percentage inhibition of 62.918 percent. The concentration at which 50% inhibition occurs is known as the IC₅₀. According to the above results, 50% inhibition of plant extract occurs between 60 and 80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (75.51 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), while ascorbic acid occurs between 40 and 60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ (42.084 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). The extract had a good ability to scavenge radicals. Figure 18 illustrates the correlation between the concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) and the percentage of inhibition for ascorbic acid and plant extract. For both samples, the percentage of inhibition rises with increasing concentration. At all doses, ascorbic acid has greater antioxidant activity than the extract, as evidenced by its steeper slope and higher inhibition values.

Fig. 18. Relationship between concentration, and % inhibition of extract and ascorbic acid.

CONCLUSION:

The phytochemical composition, pharmacognostic properties, and biological activities of the bark part of *T. ivorensis* were all carefully evaluated in this study. Secondary metabolites, including tannins, phenolic substances, flavonoids, steroids, and glycosides, were detected in the hydromethanolic extract by qualitative phytochemical analysis. Pharmacognostic analysis, which covered both macroscopic and microscopic inspection, provided crucial diagnostic aspects for plant identification and quality control. The hydromethanolic extract showed

significant biological activity, including anthelmintic and antibacterial qualities, supporting its traditional medical use. Based on its antioxidant qualities, the plant might be a natural source of antioxidants. For additional pharmacological and toxicological research to investigate its therapeutic potential, these findings provide a solid scientific foundation.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

The writers of this article state that they have no relevant conflicts of interest.

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